

BASIC PRINCIPLES OF OPERATION OF ANALOG TELEVISION TRANSMITTERS

Ismatov Shahboz Abdulhakim ugli

Termez State University, Master of Information Technology

shakhbozcheek@gmail.com

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.6669732>

Annotation: Technological developments relating to Broadcasting have been progressing very rapidly. That is the workings, systems, and devices in the broadcasting system contained in radio stations and television stations, as well as the receiver's development can also receive from the broadcasting station broadcasters. The workings of systems and devices that are commonly used systems of radio and television broadcasting stations are commonly operated by operators in order to broadcast to listeners or spectator viewers broadcasting stations.

Keywords: Broadcasting system, television station, method, device, receiver, ICT.

INTRODUCTION

Broadcasting is the dissemination of audio and video content to a scattered audience through radio, television, or other media. The recipient can be a large public or some large public group (See Wikipedia on the definition of broadcasting). The origin of the term broadcasting refers to the phenomenon in agricultural land on the activity of spreading the seeds in vast land.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Broadcasting aimed at a very narrow range of audience called narrow casting. In line with the technological developments of electronic components of broadcasting systems exist 3 systems are used, there is ¹:

- broadcasting radio
- broadcasting tv (tv broadcasting)
- internet broadcasting (Streaming Radio and Television Streaming)

The discovery of a television system is transmissions by sound (audio) and image (video) signals. There are three interrelated parts, namely TV studios, TV transmitters and TV receivers. The principle block diagram of a television broadcast system can be described in block diagram as in the following image 1.1:

Image 1.1. Communication Broadcasting TV Broadcasting System

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The types of production that can be transmitted is the result of field production and studio production that is processed by using equipment:

1. Field Production

ENG (Electronic News Gathering) - Electronic News Production The process of video recording of news types using portable devices such as portable VCR cameras and 1 microphone, with a cameraman crew accompanied by a director who also doubles as a reporter. EFP (Electronic Field Production) - Electronic Field Production Same as ENG, only types of programs produced are documentary, *sinetron* (film style). MCR (Multi Camera Remote) Field Production using more camera and 1 microphone, with switchers, multiple monitors, sound system audio. Production recorded is *sinetron*, music, sport, etc².

2. Studio Production

Live - The program is broadcast live, the stage of production is the final stage in the process. Most news programs, sports, state ceremonies are broadcast live.

Video Taping

(recorded in video tape) Live on Tape Production goes on without stopping, until the end of the program, editing only in special cases (insert editing).

Recorded segment³.

Works In order to work and display images from your favorite TV stations, the television consists of parts that support each other to work. Broadly speaking the television parts are Antenna, Power

² Grob, Benard (2014), Basic Television and Video System: Principles and Servicing, New York : Mc Graw Hill.

³ Coolen, John (2014), Electronic Communication, Ontario: Lakehead University Thunder Bay. Indra Wibawa, (2011) Modul Dasar Produksi Televisi, Fakultas Ilmu Komunikasi, UMB

supply (power), Tuner, Rangkain video detector, Video amplifier suite, and Audio Series. The following outline the way television works(see image 1.2)

Image 1.2. How Television works

Working Principle In Image

Viewer Tool The development stage of the drawing tool used today is actually divided into two phases. The first phase in 1855 was marked by the discovery of cathode ray tubes by German scientist Heinrich Geißler. He is the father of the tube monitor. Then,

33 years later, Austrian chemist Friedrich Reinitzer laid the foundation for developing LCD technology by discovering liquid crystals. The tube technology since the beginning was developed for realizing monitors.

a. CRT

In 1897 Karl Ferdinand Braun, a German scientist who made a television (TV) tube (cathode ray tube / CRT). The image tube in the receiver converts the video signal back into visual information. The electron file

b. LCD

LCD technology is not really a new thing. The LCD was first tested in RCA's electronic lab laboratory in the United States, by George Heilmeyer in 1968⁴.

He tested LCD-based dynamic scattering mode (DSM). A year later, Optel's Heilmeyer company then produced the LCD. LCD commonly used to display audio visual. This LCD performs electrical control on the light by polarizing the existing liquid crystals on the media cells that apply the LCD.

Image 1.3. CRT Tubes

⁴ Suartini, Tuti (2013) Teknik Broadca
Robin, Michael (2010), Digital Televis
ork : John Wiley & Sons.

Polarization is done after there is electrical contact on the fluids that exist on the cells on the TV. The three LCD system also has better image processing capabilities, resulting in better images as well

Image 1.4. How LCD works

c. OLED

Color TV OLED information is produced using an organic carbon-based mixture, which emits red, blue and green light in response to electric currents. OLED The ultimate difference from LCDs in the absence of backlight and no "to crooked" crystals. No additional light source is needed to energize organic mixtures, so they use very little power and can be produced with a thin profile. OLED TV panels come with either two or three layers that are organically mixed; lies a great thin layer of "glass". The panel is supported by a plexiglass material that also protects sensitive inside materials. In addition to images, the television transmitter also carries the sound signals transmitted along with the image signal.

References:

1. Simon, Haykin (2019), An Introduction to Analog & Digital Communication, New York : John Wiley & Sons.
2. Suhana, Shoji, Shigeki, (2011), Buku Pegangan Teknik Telekomunikasi, Jakarta : PT Pradya Paramitra.
3. Grob, Benard (2014), Basic Television and Video System: Principles and Servicing, New York : Mc Graw Hill.
4. Coolen, John (2014), Electronic Communication, Ontario: Lakehead University Thunder Bay.
5. Indra Wibawa, (2011) Modul Dasar Produksi Televisi, Fakultas Ilmu Komunikasi, UMB
6. Taub H., Schilling D., (2014), Principles of Communications Systems, New York : Mc Graw Hill.
7. Teuber, Jan, (2013), Digital Image Processing, New York : Prentice Hall.

7. Suartini, Tuti (2013) Teknik Broadcasting, Bahan ajar teknik broadcasting PLPG, Universitas Pendidikan Indonesia
- Robin, Michael (2010), Digital Television Fundamental : Design and Installation of Video and Audio Systems, New York : John Wiley & Sons.

